

The Relativity of Quantum Phenomena

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Abstract:

This article is trying to reinterpret the principle and mechanism hidden in Double-slit experiment in a more comprehensible view, and demonstrate a new perspective, which could better explain existent phenomena, partially reconcile the divergence between Quantum Theory and Relativity Theory, and cautiously forecast possible relevant application direction.

1. Doubts from Double-slit experiment

Distinguished Mr. Richard Feynman once told us, "Double-slit experiment, has in it the heart of quantum mechanics, contains the only mystery of quantum mechanics."

To reveal the myster, various experiments have been performed. Most of them can be subsumed into categories below:

- (1) Original version
- (2) Individual particles version
- (3) "Which-way" version
- (4) Delayed choice version
- (5) Quantum eraser version
- (6) Weak measurement version
- (7) Other versions

Nearly all the experiment results include one or several features: irrationality, unpredictability, non-objectivity, anti-commonsense, etc.

To explain above experiment results, the weird behavior, phenomenon displayed in experiment process and, at most important, the mechanism behind them, various interpretation versions prevail once or to this day.

2. Redefined concepts

To better explain following points of view pertaining to the experiments and the doubts, several concepts will be clarified beforehand:

(1) Observation

There are different types of measurements, like quantum measurement, classical measurement or other types. But one kind of measurement or observation, which is more general, will be defined. Even the observed system is not necessary to interact with any laboratory device or instrument located in observing system.

When one system is interacting with outer system, to exchange information with outer system, in other words, to induce relevance, it means the observation has occurred.

The interaction form can be in different kinds:

Attracted by gravity, projected by photon, touched by a hand, glanced by a naked eye, blocked by a barrier, etc. No matter which kind of interaction happens, it means the observation has occurred.

Depending on the quantity of information acquired from observed system, observation could be divided into Slight Observation, Normal Observation and Complete Observation. There is no exact boundary

between each two of them. They are just given as qualitative conceptions.

Slight Observation means very minor information acquired, like only in one dimension, or in one freedom of motion or even less than that. Complete Observation means nearly all information acquired, which may also makes the observed system become one part of observing system. And Normal Observation is something between them.

This part could be concluded: **The Observation of objects, behaviors or phenomena should be the progress of acquiring and receiving information from observed system by relative observing system.**

However, another kind of interaction should be noticed, which will erase relevant information from outer system, in other words, to reduce relevance between two systems. Besides, interaction without relative information acquired or erased is also possible.

(2) Certainty

This concept is more widely known about another name of it, wave-particle duality, which actually is not the most explicit way to describe trait of objects. As it should be realized, microscopic objects constitute macroscopic world. Hence the former one should have the most fundamental property.

But human being live in macroscopic world, so it is often take for granted that macroscopic world is the most objective one. Particle or wave, all come from the concept of our daily experience. Particle means behaving like a ball. Wave means behaving like water.

Using these two concepts to comprehend a more fundamental one, it surely will cause some doubts. So the best way is to temporarily forego something we are familiar with in macroscopic world, and use the more fundamental one to re-learn it.

Microscopic objects, which constitute the macroscopic world, have following properties:

A) They can evolve smoothly while isolated from outer system. If no observation is performed, normally they will not be shown in any circumstance to the latter

one.

B) When observed by one outer system, they will be connected, cohered, entangled or in other words, linked to this one, which means the information be partially or completely acquired by the latter one.

C) With different degree of observation, the microscopic objects will show different behavior trait to the outer system. The more observation performed, the more information acquired, and the more certainty behaved. Vice versa. Anyway, one wave function can represent the state.

D) This observation is one kind of interaction, which will cause microscopic object linked to outer system. Stronger link, like force between Fe atoms in iron ball, causes more certain behavior, and makes a ball behave like a particle. Weaker link, like force between H₂O molecules in water, causes more uncertain behavior, and makes water behave like wave.

In above description, some content still remain the same with Copenhagen interpretation ^[1], but it will make the behavior of quantum shown in double-slit experiment seem not so weird.

Regarding the factors that affect certainty, whether Macroscopic or Microscopic is not important, also whether Classical or Quantum is not critical. The most important one is the difficulty level to interact with outer system, to exchange information with outer system, in other words, to induce relevance.

The Macroscopic objects or Classical systems, have too much information included and keep on exposing them to outer system, which lead to an important fact that our daily observable world be linked tightly as an undivided and certain one.

On the contrary, the Microscopic objects or so called Quantum system is relatively easier to be isolated from other system, partially or nearly completely, which means it's easier to be achieved in experiment.

This part could be concluded: **The certainty of objects, behaviors or phenomena should be directly related to the quantity of information observed from observed system by relative observing system.**

(3) Existence

When it comes to existence, the boundary between Science and Philosophy seems obscure. Hence, this concept should be described more rigorously. **Whether objects, behaviors or phenomena are existent, should be relative.**

If one system is existent, it should interact with outer system, to exchange information with outer system, to induce relevance, to become observable. It is more rigorous to describe like: One system is existent relative to outer system.

If one system have no interaction with outer system, no exchange of information, or no relevance, not observable, it should be described as: One system is not existent relative to outer system. But it doesn't disqualify the existence of it. We can describe: One system is existent relative to itself.

In some really special circumstance, it can be described like: One system is existent relative to a new outer system, which is not the same one with our daily world.

(4) Objectivity

Another concept approaching Philosophy field. It's also the synonym of authenticity. **Whether objects, behaviors or phenomena are objective, should be relative.**

As our daily experience, all the observable world or universe is united as a whole objective one, which often be used as a criteria to verify the objectivity of other objects or systems. Only standing on one angle sometime can get correct conclusion, but not objectively correct enough. When standing on another angle, the situation may be different.

From above content, the existence has different conclusion when the observed system is compared with different outer systems. When relativity is considered when defining objectivity, it makes the latter one perfect.

That's all the concepts needed to be redefined. And

with so many relative concepts, it unavoidably cause us to remember another fundamental theory. It will be detailed in following content.

3. Reinterpretation of Double-slit experiment

With above pavement, it's time to indicate the explanation for experiments in above categories. In the same category, different specific experiments showed similar feature. So only one typical specific experiment is cited in each category.

(1) Original version

In this version, conducted by Thomas Young in 1801, the phenomenon can be well explained either in classical or quantum way. So no need to repeat.

(2) Individual particles version^[2]

The general feature of this version is that even when single particle was emitted, it also behaved like wave, seemed going through two slits in the same time, and then interacted with itself. However, when it finally hit the screen, there was only one light point, seeming like a particle. But multiple points still formed on screen the interference pattern.

There is already a Copenhagen interpretation for this phenomenon as Complementarity principle: "A particular experiment can demonstrate particle or wave property, but not both at the same time." Actually it is only a surface interpretation. Another one, which is more comprehensible, will be proposed below:

In this version, when the microscopic object went through two slits, this kind of interaction actually cause some information lost, the path. Also due to the size of the microscopic object, it is hard for outer system to acquire this information again. So it can only behave in an uncertain way, like wave.

When the microscopic object interacted with screen, the lost information came back. So it can behave in a certain way, like a particle.

Interference pattern shown on screen behind slits is only one kind of shadow, which could represent how much certainty of the microscopic objects have shown to outer system. Also represent how many information

the outer system have got from the microscopic objects, how much the outer system know about the microscopic objects.

To better understand this statement, I suggest to imagine our outer system as a computer, which has adequate ability to compute and draw a well-defined picture, provided that there is enough input data.

If there is very limited information inputted, but still force it to finish the drawing, apparently the output will only be a vague one. That's all what it could do based on the preconditions, so does our outer system.

The common point of them is: They don't know how to show it, but they need to show it, so they can only show an approximate and uncertain picture. In other words, they are both cheated, they have no other solution, so they can only compromise.

And one more thing need to be noticed is that when the path information came back, those single particles still gradually composed interference pattern on screen. It seemed that the progress of interference between two paths really happened, even if it is a compromised one. That means once our system accepted the uncertainty, it also accepted the consequences.

The uncertainty leads to two consequences, one is splitting into two parts, the other is to interacting with each other. Only the second one remains, which means only this kind of interaction during uncertainty period will remain.

From this version, we can conclude that our outer system, which also can be generalized to the scope of already known universe, will in some case allow this phenomenon happen:

If one system only have limited information exposed to other system, the behavior which showed in the latter one could be presented in an uncertain way.

The less information exposed, the less certain behavior showed, and vice versa.

If this kind of uncertainty unavoidably lead to a consequence, in which different uncertain states will interact with each other, then even after the

uncertainty cleared, the effect of interaction remain.

(3) "Which-way" version^[3]

The general feature of this version is that particle seemed to pass through two slits in the same time, but impossible to determine which one. All kinds of experiments attempt to detect the specific path while keeping its wave behavior, but not successful.

Complementarity principle given by Copenhagen interpretation can also explain this behavior. Anyway another explanation will be proposed, which is more acceptable by proponents of Relativity Theory.

As Special Relativity Theory told us, "The laws of physics are invariant (i.e. identical) in all inertial frames of reference (i.e. non-accelerating frames of reference)."

The microscopic particle is in a motion, relative to the outer system, with speed equal or near to light, along a path that could be described by one wave function. This is the conclusion from our observation angle.

Let's suppose the particle itself also can observe, think, analyze and conclude, the picture in its mind would be different: The outer system is in a motion, relative to me, with speed equal or near to light, along a path that could be described by one wave function, which probably the same one they will use to describe mine.

In that case, the two slits in the description of wave function partially merged with each other. And the merged part was the most possible path for particle. There wasn't any problem about how to choose, because there was no choice for the particle at all.

Even if the particle wondered, the way it went through just now belonged to which slit, there was no answer. Because the information it acquired from the outer system was also very limited, which could't support the particle to figure it out. But its own system also accept the outer system to behave to it with an uncertain way.

If we really want to know, whether the particle split or not, which way it finally chose and what happened during that period? What is the truth? The most suitable answer is: It depends...

It depends on which observation system we stand in. If in outer system, the particle split, behaved like wave, passed through two slits in the same time, then interfered with itself and finally hit the screen. The effect of splitting disappeared, and that of interfering remained.

If in the system of the particle, it always stood still like a particle, and the channel which seemed to be the mixture of two wave-behaved slits passed through it. The also wave-behaved screen seemed to interfere with itself, while coming towards particle. Anyway, the particle stood still. At the moment of path information coming back, which means screen hit the particle, it was found its past path is not a straight line, and there was a deflected light point from center of screen, which occasionally could compose some pattern with other previous particles.

With above transformation of observation systems, or transformation of reference frames, the particle will find the answer:

First, it didn't split, and never would it, because it had 100% certainty for itself. In its own view, it was a pure particle.

Second, it didn't choose any way, because there was no choice. What it could do is standing still.

At last, it also didn't know what happened during that period, because the outer system behaved in a marvelous way. The reason was lack of information received for itself to analyze.

This is the truth given by particle, which is in a relatively uncertain system compared to ours.

From this version, we can conclude:

If one system behaves in an uncertain way to another system due to the lack of information, the equivalent uncertainty of the second system will be observed by the first system.

The uncertainty described by wave function should be invariant in any inertial reference frame.

The conclusion for the truth can be different, due to the lack of information between different observing systems. But the uncertainty always remain true.

The above description didn't disobey any cornerstone of current Quantum Theory. But it is more comprehensible and more compatible with other theories.

(4) Delayed choice version ^[4]

The most famous one of this version is Wheeler's delayed choice experiment. When the second splitter inserted, one light would always be on; when the second splitter not inserted, two lights were on alternately. But inserting happened after path choosing, which looked like a delaying choice.

Actually no matter the second splitter inserted or not, the photon would go along two paths through the first splitter, with a wave-like behavior. The difference is before hitting on detector, whether the interaction of two paths happened or not.

If happened, the effect of interaction remained, and only one light would always be on. If not happened, the effect would disappear, and two lights would be on alternatively in random.

We can see there is no delayed choice. But the participation of human consciousness is interesting. In this version a human consciousness was making choice, to interact with surrounding circumstances and to cause consequences. This is similar with what we did in daily life.

Also in this version, we can imagine to replace the human decision method with another one, like what Mr. Schrödinger would like to do. For example, to put a radioactive source with a decaying probability into previous experiment, as well as relevant detector, counter, controller and actuator. Preset a definite quantity of radioactive particles received by detector in a certain period be the threshold value to trigger the actuator. Once actuator triggered, it will put the second beam splitter into the path.

The probability of decay, the threshold value, the

trigger logic of actuator and other factors can be preset and controlled. Just like we told a man, who participate this experiment, how to operate, do it totally randomly, or randomly in the scope of rule, or in a definite way.

In this case, the alternative experiment will get the same results with the previous one. And if only distinguished via experiment results, it is very hard for us to tell which one is conducted by a real human's consciousness.

From this version, we can conclude:

Human consciousness in daily life also behave in a similar way with quantum. With different pre-control methods, we can get random result, definite result or only probability predictable result.

(5) Quantum eraser version^[5]

General feature of this version: Marking path information, interference pattern disappeared; erasing path information, pattern reappeared. It seemed like quantum was playing game with us.

Actually as described above, the interference pattern shown on the screen is only one kind of shadow, which could represent how much certainty of the microscopic objects have shown to outer system.

The path information is erased from our system, so object behaved in a wave-like type in aspect of path. Hence, the interference pattern was inevitable. When marked, path information back, as well as the particle behavior.

From this version, we can conclude:

Path information, which also can be generalized to the scope of any aspect of information, can be erased or marked repeatedly.

Once erased, uncertainty will appear. After re-marked, certainty will come back.

Also we can try to keep on erasing every single aspect of information, and make object be totally erased, like becoming even invisible.

(6) Weak measurement version^[6]

General feature of this version: Only very limited

observation performed, to the extent of slight impact on the interference pattern. At the same time, particle path information can be almost determined. It seemed like the behavior of particle and wave can appear at the same time.

Actually it is also explained clearly via previous conclusion, with mechanism like Slight Observation. The interference pattern shown on screen is only one kind of shadow, which represent how much certainty of the microscopic objects have shown to outer system.

The more information shown, the more certainty displayed, and vice versa. There are not only these two states, particle or wave. Actual state can be something between them, based on how much certainty have been acquired. But these intermediate states can't be seemed as a particle or wave thoroughly. It's really something between them.

From this version, we can conclude:

If only very limited observation (i.e. Slight Observation) proceeded, limited to the extent that only affect the interference pattern slightly. In that case the particle-like behavior and wave-like behavior can be shown in the same, but neither of them is 100% pure. The state is something between them.

There is no absolute wave, no absolute particle. Only certainty is absolute.

As stated many times, the interference pattern is only one kind of shadow, just like tree shadow on the ground. When wind crosses, shadow waves. More wind, more movement of shadow. Less wind, less movement. No wind, no movement.

We can also deduce from that case, it is wind makes shadow wave. But it's not the most essential fact. Actually the wind interacts with tree. More wind, more movement of tree.

Wind can be compared to observation, tree to observed system, and ground to observing system. Then movement of tree should be behaving like a particle, and standing still be like wave. And at last, standing still of shadow is the pattern, and moving direction is the path.

With minimum degree of wind, we can still find the shadow almost stand still. When we gradually enhance the power of wind, the shadow begins to move slightly, and can be identified as moving to left or right. So we conclude, with not strong wind, it is possible to find which direction the shadow move to, and in the same time the shadow remains almost standing still. This is the inner nature of weak measurement.

Also we can conclude, it is not possible for the wind to make the shadow obviously move to one direction and totally stand still, at the same time. It can also be called as complementarity principle.

The essence is interaction between wind and tree. As for shadow, only a common appearance. No need to insisting on acquiring both path and pattern in the same time.

(7) Other versions^[7]

Besides all the above mentioned variations, a large quantity of other versions were conducted. But herein, only a specific one would be quoted. The one conducted by Mr. Yoon-Ho Kim, R. Yu, S.P. Kulik, Y.H. Shih, and Marlon O. Scully, in 1999.

I personally admire this version very much. It has included all the elements mentioned above: Individual particles, "Which-way", Delayed choice, Quantum eraser, and Weak measurement. It's wonderful.

Most of the elements have been explicitly elaborated in above content. Only one element I would like to explain more, delayed choice.

The most attracting part is "The information of a quantum can be erased or marked even after registration of its entangled twin". This behavior unavoidably lead us to find an acceptable reason.

In Special Relativity Theory, there are some very basic principle already proved many times by numerous facts, which we don't need to question their correctness:

"Two events, simultaneous for one observer, may not be simultaneous for another observer if the observers are in relative motion."

"Moving clocks are measured to tick more slowly

than an observer's "stationary" clock".

"Objects are measured to be shortened in the direction that they are moving with respect to the observer".

Based on above three principles, even with no calculation, we can get the answer:

The photon is in a relative motion compared to our experiment system. The relative velocity is in light speed, so in the view of photon, our system should be shortened to 0 length in the direction of its motion, and our time will be frozen. Although it will change direction several times, but once it change to another direction, our system will be shortened to 0 length in the same one.

The reflection of light is something different from acceleration, so General Relativity is not considered in this case.

With above transformation of reference frame, the photon should find itself went through the whole route until hit one detector, in no time. Also in the same time when its entangled twin hit another detector.

It means all these behavior happened in the same time of photon's system, because there is no distance between each spots in its route, to enable itself spend any time.

If measured in Minkowski space, the space-time distance between each point of the photon route is 0, which means happening in the same time and same place. It's normal for it to know all the information instantaneously.

Now back to the experiment process:

The photon went through two slits, got refracted or reflected several times, hit detector D_1 (or D_2), in the same time. And meanwhile its entangled twins met at D_0 to form interference pattern, in the same time.

Also the photon could go through two slits, got refracted or reflected several times, hit detector D_3 (or D_4), get the lost information back, and make previous two-slit path confirmed to one, in the same time. And meanwhile its entangled twins met at D_0 , but due to the back acquired path information, cause only one twin

remain, without any interference pattern.

The above explanation will naturally lead us to further consider:

If the particle is not photon, but other one with measurable mass and lower speed, what will happen? If the situation is true, why we can still find the process is finished not in the same time? If different observers find different conclusions, what is the truth?

Via considering these question, it unavoidably force us to face the most untouchable fundamental law, no matter in Physics or other science, which is causality. We must be very cautious.

First, not only photon is transmitted with velocity of light. Fields as well as causality itself are also considered to be transmitted with velocity of light relative to any observing system. That means there will be the same effect no matter it's photon or other particle, or even macroscopic object. When causality is transmitted with velocity of light relative to us, it also means there is no space for it to spend even a little time.

Then, it is still relativity. In the view of causality, if it has, it finishes all its job instantaneously. But in our sight, it's only finished in light speed.

At last, there is no absolute truth, only absolute relativity.

From this version, we can conclude:

The eigenvalue of the state of one object, behavior, phenomenon, or system will only be 100% accurately observed by itself.

Any other observing system, which have relative motion, or relative uncertainty to the observed one, will only get deflected conclusion.

Once the eigenvalue established, the causality will be transmitted instantaneously, but the effect will be revealed to other observers only in a light speed.

At last, I consider it helpful to conduct one extended version, and would like to detail my consideration in following content, not here as some conclusions of already proceeded experiment.

4. Explanation of relevant typical phenomena

With all the above definitions and conclusions derived from various double-slit experiments, other dilemmas, phenomena or doubts could be able to get re-evaluated.

(1) Erwin Schrödinger's Cat

This thought experiment itself is easy to explain. We can find some relevant information already unavoidably exposed, even not observed by human outside box.

The detector knew the status of radioactive source, the actuator knew the status of detector, the hammer knew the status of actuator, and the bottle knew the status of hammer... Even the ground can feel whether the cat is walking or laying down for several days.

If we consider only the cat belongs to observed system, and other belongs to observing system, the status is confirmed in the very beginning. If consider only the human belongs to observing system, and other belongs to observed system, the status of the cat is really in superposition.

If we think deeper, what will be different if we put a tiger in box, instead of radioactive source, or put a human with knife in? The result of poor cat can be different, but one thing will remain the same, that is the observer outside box still can't know the result of the cat.

The fixed 50% decaying probability, and the more random, more unpredictable behavior of human or tiger seems a difference. But if we spend a period of time as long as a tiger's life to design, build, and keep updating a complicated quantum system, it is also possible to make nobody can calculate the probability of this system.

In the contrary, if we enforce very special, very strict rules to training a human or even tiger, it's also possible to control the probability of certain behavior.

There is another simple case in our daily life: Whether your daughter is at home. Suppose you are on your way back home, told by your wife to prepare

lunch for your daughter, provided that she has already been back from school.

Whether your daughter is at home? Perhaps the information has been acquired by the TV controller in her hand, or the sofa beneath her body, but you don't have. Your cellphone is out of battery, which can't help to acquiring information.

You remember your daughter only like fish, but you like mutton. So with limited money, the best choice is to purchase both with less quantity.

After you get home you find your daughter is not at home. This uncertainty have been confirmed. But the fish can't be returned back...

This is really similar with what happened in double-slit experiment.

Before one choice made, no one else would know it. Even after choice made, but not shown to others, or not interacting with surrounding circumstances, no one else would know what it would be. Only the one who made decision will know what his choice is.

Once the choice made and proceeded, the definite effect will be shown. If keeping indecisive, the expectation for future will be obscure, and may suffer unpredictable deflection until confirmed.

From the above description, we can conclude:

Superposition status can also occur in macroscopic world, provided that no method from the observer can be applied to acquire the relative information from observed system.

Consciousness decision has similar driving mechanism with quantum decision, or at least similar effect.

(2) Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox ^[8]

This one (with abbreviation of EPR paradox) is also well known. A simplistic judgement, Einstein or Bohr, who is correct, would be reckless. Instead, it is more preferable to give answer based on above definitions and conclusions.

First, the most controversial part is the two principles: Principle of locality and principle of realism.

A) Regarding principle of locality, it can be explained by previous conclusion: Once the eigenvalue of one particle established, the causality will be transmitted instantaneously to its twin particle.

In this experiment, although the two particles were divided to rather large distance, but in the view of light-speed transmitted causality, there was no distance, also no time could be spend. Any newly received effect on one particle would be transmitted to another one instantaneously.

It seems principle of locality doesn't apply. But it doesn't make Einstein lose. I believe his original purpose is not to verify principle of locality. He was trying to create a paradox, which is deduced from Quantum Theory, and not compatible to one already existing truth. Principle of locality is only the presupposed "truth". His original purpose is principle of realism.

B) Regarding principle of realism, it also can be explained by previous conclusion: The eigenvalue of the state of one object, behavior, phenomenon, or system will only be 100% accurately observed by itself. Any other observing system, which have relative motion, or relative uncertainty to the observed one, will only get deflected conclusion.

That means realism really exist, but only can be observed by itself. Once observed, it will show us a result similar to its eigenvalue, but never the original one. In one words, the realism exists, but is relative.

Also foresaid realism only means those status, which can make sense without comparing to other system. Other status, like velocity or position, must have compared system. Talking about them without compared system doesn't make sense.

Second, let's see what happened in this experiment. Two entangled particles, were created, isolated, and separated to a large distance. The initial status of them were opposite, fixed at the moment they were created, then remained unchanged, or could be evolving internally in some special cases, but always in opposite status.

Once observed, the status of observed particle will be revealed to us, and lose the entanglement with another. Also isolation broken, and internal evolving ended. The not observed one would remain the opposite status recorded at the moment previous observation occurred, until we tried to observe it and surprisingly found it is just in the opposite status.

It's different from wave function collapse principle. But it will depict the same picture as the former one, and more acceptable by opponent of the former one. It's not collapse. It's already there. It really resemble with collapse, because only when the time of "collapse", can we get the required information.

From above description, there isn't obvious over-distant interaction between two particles revealed, but it doesn't deny its existence. Also even if over-distant interaction exist, it doesn't disprove Einstein's understanding to realism. Einstein realized part of the real meaning of realism, but use a not very suitable compared truth to prove it.

Wave function collapse is only a surface appearance, but it doesn't makes Bohr lose either. Bohr regard the behavior, which can be acquired by observer most similar to realism, as realism itself. It's hard to be judged as right or wrong. But his opinion about the weakness of EPR paradox is correct.

So this duel, 1:1, score tied. We can find both Relativity Theory and Quantum Theory are correct. They cooperate tightly in this paradox, to compose a marvelous story for us.

Also we can think deeper, about the not revealed over-distance interaction. Actually there is a more common name, entanglement. Does it really exist? Sure.

First, there is sufficiency. Because the causality transmitted instantaneously. It has the ability to accomplish this task.

Second, there is necessity. The two particles are isolated from outer system, in some certain aspects, in a great extent. When evolving, the most possible way is to interact with the entangled twin, not the outer system.

Once entanglement established, the status of twin particles will remain still or change simultaneously. Being in opposite status is only one method of entanglement. Because using method like decaying or SPDC (abbreviation for spontaneous parametric down conversion) is more achievable in nowadays period. And this kind of method always produce particles in opposite status.

Once observed, new entanglement will be established between observed one and observing system, meanwhile previous entanglement between two particles will be disbanded, which can also be called as decoherence. The two particles will separately remain in the status, which is determined at the moment of first observation. It looks like they have over-distance interaction.

If before observation, another kind of interaction is performed, which will change status of one particle and not acquire any information from it, the status of interacted particles will change, but entanglement with its twin remain. There is no other interactions, so the consequence of change can only be transmitted to the twin in the same isolated system instantaneously, and then reveal to us in a light speed. That's real over-distance interaction.

From the above description, we can conclude:

The interactions between systems can be consumed into three categories:

Observation: It will cause relative information exposed from observed system to observing system, which will increase the certainty of behavior shown by observed system to observing system. One of its side effect is to cause decoherence from observed system and entanglement to observing system.

Omission: It will cause relative information of observed system eliminated from observing system, which will decrease the certainty of behavior shown by observed system to observing system. One of its side effect is to cause decoherence from observing system.

Operation: It will only change the status of observed system, and will not cause relative

information in observing system increase or decrease. One of its side effect is to cause over-distance interaction.

(3) Bell's inequality^[9]

This one is an unavertable challenge. Many versions of verification have been done to test it. The core idea is about the existence of hidden variable theory.

Obviously from above content, local hidden variable theory could not be found, because the causality is transmitted instantaneously. Will there be non-local hidden variable theory?

Actually due to the relative motion of light speed between different systems, non-locality is already hidden in Special Relativity. Also the invariant laws of physics in different systems can better help to understand uncertainty, objectivity, realism and other phenomenon of quantum.

From the above description, we can conclude:

Special Relativity Theory is one of the best candidate for non-local hidden variable theory, if really needed.

The key was always in Einstein's pocket. Maybe he just didn't want to use it in that way.

(4) Entropy

In previous content, information, this word are mentioned many times. In Physics, it has an academic name, entropy. In nowadays science field, it mainly have two aspects of usage, in Thermodynamics and in Informatics.

In Thermodynamics, it is expressed in form of the second law of Thermodynamics, which also represent the direction of time arrow. In Informatics, it is also expressed as the uncertainty of expected results, which could be reduced via acquiring relevant information.

Actually there is some relations between them:

The information entropy is part of the whole entropy that one object or event possesses. The more proportion of information entropy is, the

more uncertainty the object or event shows.

The way of reducing information entropy is acquiring information, which need observation be performed, or work be done. The more we know about this object or event, the less uncertainty it shows.

When proportion of information entropy equals to 0, it means we totally know all the information about it. When this proportion equals to 1, it means we know nothing about it.

The inner nature of Uncertainty Principle is when we try to reduce information entropy via observation, we create new information entropy, which cause us never be able to reduce the proportion of information entropy equals to 0.

The three interactions between systems summarized above can be checked.

Omission: Uncertainty increased, and the whole entropy of observed system increased. Consistent with the second law of Thermodynamics.

Operation: Interacting with observed system without doing work. Uncertainty or entropy not reduced. Not violate the second law of Thermodynamics.

Observation: It will do work to observed system and cause uncertainty reduce, as well as entropy, which also not violate the second law of Thermodynamics.

Uncertainty will not reduce automatically, unless observation proceeded, which means work be done. So the interactions or behaviors of quantum shown in series of experiments didn't violate the second law of Thermodynamics.

We can reduce proportion of information entropy to make something more visible. Or increase proportion to make object or behavior more invisible. Wave function can be seemed as one way to depict it.

(5) Black hole

Macroscopic objects have great quantity of entropy, which means great quantity of information to acquire, and also abundant methods enables us to acquire.

Microscopic objects have few quantity of entropy, which means few quantity of information to acquire,

and also very limited methods left for us to acquire.

Different proportion of information acquired in total information cause different degree of certainty. And not acquired part is foresaid information entropy.

In cosmology, one kind of peculiar object, with huge quantity of entropy, but only leave us very limited ways to observe, is called black hole.

The total entropy of it didn't lose, but perfectly hidden behind event horizon. So the second law of Thermodynamics could survive. We can only know there is a huge quantity of entropy, or even do some calculation via area of sphere. However, there is no possible way for us to know what the information exactly is. In this way, this kind of celestial sphere exists in a highly uncertain way relative to us. Of course, if only concerning mass, electric charge or angular momentum, it's pretty certain.

The most incomprehensible part is singularity. When doing calculation, infinitely large mass density caused by infinitely small volume makes no sense. But when Uncertainty Principle considered in, it will be different.

The reason of Uncertainty Principle mainly used for microscopic world is the easily triggered disturbance. Macroscopic world with large mass is relative hard to show this kind of disturbance. Considering the mass of singularity, there will be extremely minor uncertainty shown. But no matter how minor, it will cause a finite result, which means singularity will be located and quivering in an extremely narrow space, distributed as per one probability function, with extremely near to 100% probability at the center point of event horizon, but not 100%. This time the probability distribution can also be described as density distribution. This sounds ridiculous, but I believe Mr. Duc de Broglie will also agree.

From above description, I would like give following hypothesis:

Some confusing extreme value could be avoided via correct and appropriate usage of Uncertainty Principle, just like the explanation given to the third law of Thermodynamics.

(6) Dark Matter and Dark Energy

In previous content, it is mentioned that in some really special circumstance, one system may be existent relative to a new outer system, which is not the same one shown in our daily life. Another suspensive object in cosmology would be a good example.

Dark Matter, only gravity effect could be obviously found. One possible supposition is composed by a new particle, which have gravity effectible mass, and ruled by a new force. The gravity behaves as normal, which makes objects with mass gather. The new force provides support against gravity, just like what electromagnetic force did in our world. Other new short-range forces may apply or not, depending on further research data.

In one case, the new particles also converge to compose stars or planets revolving around center of galaxy. Even intelligent creatures would be developed from that. In this case, they will call us dark matter, because we are showing strange behavior to them, only interacting with gravity, not with other forces in their world. But we do make sense, because the supposed existence of us can interpret the unconventional phenomenon observed in rotation of galaxy.

But if dark matter is really distributed in a discrete way like stars, the effect of their gravity to observable celestial sphere should be discovered. As there isn't any relevant record found about this, more suitable status of dark matter should be in other way:

The particles stay in balance position of gravity and the new force, which makes them continuously distributed in most space of galaxy, or even beyond the border of some galaxies. The gravity will cause effect to the rotation of galaxy. And the non-interaction effect with other forces will cause stars, planets composed by normal matters move through them smoothly. This is one kind of relative existence.

By the way, the only interaction with gravity may also suggest that gravity is more special than other forces.

Dark Energy, even more mysterious, but I consider it's not something new. It is so widely distributed in our whole universe. If something is everywhere, it is nowhere. It should be some hidden characteristic we neglected. If something looks more fast than light, it should be space itself.

General Relativity Theory is correct, but also incomplete, just like Quantum Theory. The inducing of Cosmic Constant shows the non- absolutism of curvature. Actually it should also be treated as a relative parameter.

The equation of gravity field stands on the view of observer with 0 curvature. All the other space possess higher curvature than it. So it only uses Riemannian Geometry to describe universe. In most situation, our daily world curvature can be seemed near to 0, which also makes us to consider parallel straight lines never intersecting, or triangle being with 180 degree internal angle sum, this kind of thing would really happen in our daily world. But if we need to consider something happened in a place more flat than ours, it will met with problems.

To induce Cosmic Constant is a good idea, but not enough. It supposes besides curvature itself, there is other factors affecting space-time, which makes situation more complicated. It is better let curvature itself tell what will be shown to us, when something happen in a place more flat than ours.

If we consider the most flat space is with curvature 0, ours should be more than 0. If our daily world is set with curvature 0, we should also accept existence of negative curvature, which means more flat space than 0 curvature.

When standing in a high curvature place to observe low curvature place, it's just like drawing a triangle with seemingly straight line on the surface of already inflated balloon and deflate it. The triangle will shrink to inner side, in a curvature of hyperbola. That is the straightest line in lower curvature place. Also that is the path light will choose.

Negative curvature is not new in geometry or optics, but a little new in cosmology. There are two possible

results: First, it will cause light move through it, even faster than through straight line. Second, it will cause light move through it slower, just like positive curvature. Due to the inconceivability of the first one and, more important, the actual observation result of cosmological redshift, the second one is more feasible.

From above description, I would like to give following hypothesis:

The inner nature of Dark Energy, is the relative negative curvature existing among the vast space of galaxies.

The relative negative curvature will cause light behave like going through concave lens, and cause redshift with similar mechanism of positive curvature.

Even the effect of redshift is such minor due to the near to 0 absolute value, when acted on an astronomical distance, the effect will rise to an observable level.

Above is only a qualitative description. If detailed calculation is needed, treating some Constant listed in gravity field equation not as constant is a better choice. A new sub-equation should be considered into, which will enable us to describe negative curvature. For instance, Lobachevskian Geometry, or something else new.

(7) Inflation Universe and Parallel Universe

If we use the same view when comprehend Dark Energy, the big bang will be also comprehensible.

In the very beginning, our whole universe was squeezed in an extremely narrow space with extremely great curvature, in the view of latter flat space. It was in a subtle balance, that density of mass trapped by curvature, which is caused by mass itself, is just adequate to maintain the curvature.

After a minor perturbation, the balance was broken. The density was lowered with a negligible degree, but adequate enough to cause the curvature decrease in an also negligible degree, which will consequently cause the density decrease again. Then the less density of mass, the more flatness of space. The more flatness of

space, the less density of mass. And now, here we are.

Nothing can be observed spreading in space faster than light speed, but inflating speed of space itself. This is the reason that it seems to us there is a period, in which our universe seemed inflating faster than light speed.

Parallel Universe also exists, if we continue to use the relative view to define. But it's not something similar happened in different universes caused by different choices of consciousness. It is something without interaction with us.

In this case, Dark Matter is partially in the parallel universe, but not completely. If something completely in parallel universe, it means we can't recognize it, because there is no interaction with them. They can't be observed. But they exist relative to themselves.

Parallel universe can be caused with different composing particles ruled by new forces. They will not interact with our already existing forces. Also can be caused by inflation of universe. Even same kinds of force don't have time to interact with each other.

Whenever we met with problems regarding ultra-light speed, space itself is a good candidate to do contribution.

(8) Extended version of experiment

In previous content, an extended version is mentioned, based on the original one, which was conducted Mr. Yoon-Ho Kim, R. Yu, S.P. Kulik, Y.H. Shih, and Marlon O. Scully, in 1999. This thought experiment is conceived like below:

Simplify the arrangement in original experiment to cause the photon could only arrive detector D1 (or D2) to trigger interference pattern, and extend the path between slits and D1 (or D2) to an adequate distance. Inserting light absorbing plate(s) into the path before hit of D1 (or D2), to try to disable interference pattern.

Set different sub-versions based on distance relation. Use "D" to represent the distance between slits and D_0 , "I" to the distance between slits and inserting point, and "P" to the distance between slits and photon when inserting. These three distances are adjustable. But any

of them should be shorter than distance between slits and mirror M_a (or M_b).

Using left side represent shorter distance, there will be 6 different arrangements: DPI, PDI, PID, DIP, IDP and IPD. We can try to predict results one by one.

DPI: In this version, D_0 will show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will not be triggered, one point found on inserted plate.

Showing interference pattern is reasonable. If not, it will lead to a terrifying fact that we can predict change in future. But feeling terrified is not the reason to show pattern. The reason is pattern only show the prediction of future before inserting, which is that photon will arrive at D_1 (or D_2), via an unidentified path. In view of twin photons it is the future and show it on D_0 , no matter whether will be changed or not. After inserting, the prediction is that photon will hit on inserted plate, which can only be predicted by a farther D_0 , if we set.

This result demonstrates photon can forecast path in future, if no new change involved. It looks like future is perfectly forecasted. But once new change involved, the influence will cause the changed future not in accordance with previous forecast.

PDI: In this version, D_0 will not show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will not be triggered, only one point found on inserted plate.

This is the farther D_0 , mentioned in last version. When twin photons arrive D_0 , the prediction for future is being blocked by plate, which clearly show "Which-way" information. So no interference pattern shown.

This result demonstrate the same mechanism as the last one.

PID: In this version, D_0 will not show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will not be triggered, one point found on inserted plate

This is easy to explain. Photon is blocked before its twin arrive D_0 .

DIP: In this version, D_0 will show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will be triggered, no point found on inserted plate.

IDP: In this version, D_0 will show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will be triggered, no point found on inserted plate.

IPD: In this version, D_0 will show interference pattern, D_1 (or D_2) will be triggered, no point found on inserted plate.

These three versions are only set as control groups, to eliminate other wired behavior may be shown by quantum unexpectedly.

From above thought experiment and imagined results, we can conclude:

If there is no new change, future is definite. If there is, future will be changed. If there is not only one change, future will be shown as per the co-effect of each one, from the former to the latter.

If this kind thought experiment could really be done, it would be helpful.

(9) Future

From previous experiment, we consider our world has a definite future, provided that there's no new change caused by decisions. It's just like a movie constituted by numerous frames. The content is written in advance, but only revealed to us frame by frame.

Every time when new decision made, new causality will be transmitted everywhere in no time, but only revealed to us in light speed. Different decisions will be superposed in sequence of occurring, and lead to a definite future every time. This kind of superposition can be finally observed and confirmed after future revealed to us.

If only one new decision occurred with definite choice, the definite future also seems definite before shown to us. If this decision occurred with indefinite choice, the definite future seems indefinite before shown to us.

This indefinite choice can also cause superposition of status, just like different decisions occurring in the same time. It will also lead to a definite result in future, and seemingly indefinite, until finally observed and confirmed after the future revealed to us.

In short, continual decisions at present, based on the confirmed results in the past, make a relative static and ever changing future.

Decision can be made by human consciousness or quantum process. The reason why we only remember past, but not future, is because the process of forming memory is in the positive direction of the second law of Thermodynamics.

(10) Noether's theorem ^[10]

In previous content, we consider future is like a movie, composed by numerous frames. But what's the dynamic that makes objects move through frames, or makes future move towards us? To better explain it, Noether's theorem will be quoted.

The general idea of this theorem is perfect, but only two typical cases will be quoted here. Conservation of momentum and symmetry of space translation. Conservation of energy and symmetry of time translation.

In the first one, when one physical system being acted by one force, the effect will be accumulated and form an initial momentum after a period of action time. After the force removed, the initial momentum will remain unchanged and continue accumulating in the same direction. The remaining initial momentum corresponds to conservation of momentum. The following accumulated effect of initial momentum corresponds to symmetry of space translation.

Because after initial force removed, without other influence, the momentum should remain unchanged. Also without action of force, which means be in inertial system, will not be able to tell whether space translation happened by itself.

We can describe it more generally: When one physical system being acted by one force, the effect will be accumulated and form an initial state after a period of action in certain direction. After the force removed, the initial state will remain unchanged and continue accumulating in the same direction. The

remaining initial state corresponds to conservation quantity. The following accumulated effect of initial state corresponds to symmetry quantity.

We can generalize the concept of force to torque, pressure, etc. In these cases, more conservation quantity and symmetry quantity can be verified. This kind of generalization can also help to predict more non-commutability.

We can also apply the general description to the second one: When one physical system being acted by one force, the effect will be accumulated and form an initial energy after a period of action space. After the force removed, the initial energy will remain unchanged and continue accumulating in the same direction. The remaining initial energy corresponds to conservation of energy. The following accumulated effect of initial energy corresponds to symmetry of time translation.

If we consider the force only as some macroscopic propulsive force, the energy only as kinetic energy, the time only as moving time, it will perfectly answer how one object is moving in frames of time.

If we analog the force to all the fundamental forces, even if not in all of them existing conservation and symmetry relation, at least we know how the forces make everything move forward in time direction. So far all the behavior of our world can be attributed to four fundamental forces. It means we know how every single object evolves in time direction.

One typical case is the energy that makes a particle exist, which normally should be C^2 times of its mass. Once this energy acquired and particle formed, the clock commence to tick. It will force the particle to move along time direction, until the end of its life.

From the above description, we can conclude:

Effect of generalized force accumulated over generalized space will form generalized energy. No matter foresaid force continue act or not, effect of foresaid energy will continue to accumulate over foresaid space. The effect of this kind of accumulation will cause the objects once acted by foresaid force to move in the direction of time.

(11) Principle of least action^[11]

From above description, we know what makes future move to us. But how will it move? A nearly perfect answer has been given by Principle of least action. Just like the special case to explain refraction of light, choosing the soonest way, between two points.

If we ask further, why the principle of least action? How could it know the soonest way before reaching terminal point? The answer is the path is already fixed before the arrival, because causality is transmitted instantaneously. As soon as the departing from starting point, the terminal is already there. When time is driven by a certain amount of energy and make future towards us in a light speed, if there are different paths can be chosen, shorter path means sooner time. It will cause the soonest path revealed to us first. And the other choice will not be shown.

This process is similar with previous content. When the soonest path shown, adequate information got, and all the other uncertainty disappeared.

From the above description, we can conclude:

With the action of force, the starting point and terminal point is instantaneously fixed in space-time. The soonest path between them will be chosen to reveal to us, in light speed.

(12) Probability

Now, at last, here is the million dollar question, why is probability? How is the result determined? Will there be any potential factor that will affect the choice of quantum?

First, it is nearly impossible for us to create two or more exactly identical choices. Even very subtly minor difference between choices can cause different choices. Even in vacuum, quantum fluctuation also exist, which makes identical choices more impossible.

But if we really can find some method to create exactly identical choices, and let quantum system to choose, it's not surprising for them to choose any one of them. Because they are exactly the same. Choosing

anyone is reasonable.

Second, we concluded in above content, the soonest path between space-time will be chosen to reveal to us. But in some special case, like in lens imagining, the soonest way is not only one, or like the paths between two poles of a ball. Any way could be possible. When met with non-uniqueness of soonest way in space-time caused by curvature, the same thing will happen. Any way could be possible, with a certain probability.

At last it is necessary to make a clarification, that curvature here is a generalized conception. It can be like the form in double-slits experiments. In this case, actually human created an artificial curvature, to let the soonest way not unique. Another form can be called natural curvature, like atomic orbital energy level, created by nature. It is also with similar mechanism, to create separate choices, but all in soonest path. The last form is real curvature, caused by gravity, which will distribute all over space-time.

If we really need to find a more fundamental reason for probability, it should be derived from curvature.

Never absolute 0 curvature can be achieved, so always probability.

5. Relevant application direction

Many of them are already under development.

- (1) Quantum computer
- (2) Quantum communication
- (3) Quantum invisibility
- (4) Quantum intelligence
- (5) Other applications

The first two applications are relatively more common to be heard. The main restrictive factors are capability, accuracy, and anti-decoherence ability, etc. The proposed methods are like using multiple energy level system to enhance capability, using different quantum computing system parallel to verify accuracy, using suitable Operation or only limited Observation before final Observation to maintain coherence state,

etc. And hoping previous content in this article could do some help.

For the next two, there is relatively less content exposed to us.

About quantum invisibility, I would like to propose one method not found on media before, as mentioned in previous content.

Double-slit experiment is a good model. We can make a special kind of thin film, composed by several layers. The first layer is with densely arranged micro holes. Preset the size of holes and distances between them, to enable electromagnetic wave in certain range of wavelength could go through like wave. Here use holes instead of slits, to obtain diffraction or interference in all directions.

The second layers is similar, and quadruple the quantity of holes. Each holes of first layer should be located in the center of four holes of second layer. More layers could be added based on the necessity, with same mechanism.

The main principle is to use the wave trait of electromagnetic wave. When it comes through multiple paths in the same time, the energy should be seemed as divided into multiple parts, which will cause the wavelength extended to an adequately large extent, to move around objects behind film and go on spreading, without information reflected back.

About quantum intelligence, most all of them shown on media is only intelligence with quantum computing ability, not thinking ability. As I elaborated in previous content, there are many similarities between quantum mechanism and human consciousness. It should make sense, if we simulate the mechanism of it.

Double-slit experiment is a good model. Only a few detectors, actuators and controller need to be added. First we let particles choose one of the slits freely, and observe to find which slit it chose. Each slit represents one choice. Different choices detected by the detector will lead to different signal to controller. For instance, if particle passed left slit, this information will be observed by left detector, and sent to controller. Then controller send a signal to actuator, let robot raise left

hand.

Also feedback mechanism can be established. It's easy for nowadays AI to identify the expression and action of human. It's also possible to simply use electrical signal to tell robot, its previous behavior of raising left hand is commendable or not.

With affirmative signal, the laser transmitter will be slightly turned to the direction of left slit by actuator, which will slightly cause next decision have more probability to choose left slit. Vice versa. Also we can keep laser still and move slits to get the same effect.

The quantity of slits can be increased to enable multiple choices. And multiple similar systems with this mechanism can be combined together as a more complicated one. This kind of decision mechanism is not as accuracy as classical one, but it will have a trait as real human, which means unpredictable. In some special case, we need this kind of trait.

6. Summary

Via repetitive obtaining or erasing information between systems to control uncertainty state, and repetitive establishing or eliminating interaction between systems to control coherence state. Whenever we can, make the most crazy and extreme degree of these states. Before they disappear, make the most crazy and full use of them. Let the useful part remain, and the other parts gone with wind.

This is the most feasible way for us to make usage of quantum mechanism, and also the supreme right granted to us by the rules of universe.

At last, thanks to Feynman.

As he already told us "Double-slit experiment, has in it the heart of quantum mechanics, contains the only mystery of quantum mechanics."

Yes, it really does.

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